

Moroccan Electricity Mix Modeling and Optimization in Current and Future Warming Climates "E4CLIM_Bouramdane_2018-2021"

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Abstract

"E4CLIM_Bouramdane_2018-2021" is a closed-access Python software developed in the framework of the thesis [Bouramdane et al. (2021)], using inputs from the "Energy for Climate Integrated Model (E4CLIM) for Climate-Aware Renewable Energy Mixes" and adding new modules. For additional information, refer to the materials provided by this thesis in Chapter 2, "Energy System Modeling and Optimization" (p. 48–76), and Appendix A, "Theoretical Modeling Framework" (p. 156–177).

Keywords— Electricity Mix, Energy Flexibility, Climate Change.

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References

- [Bouramdane et al. (2021)] Bouramdane, A.A. Scenarios of Large-Scale Solar Integration with Wind in Morocco: Impact of Storage, Cost, Spatio-Temporal Complementarity and Climate Change. Ph.D. Thesis, Institut Polytechnique de Paris, Palaiseau, France, 2021.